

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VITREOUS FLOATERS IN A MYOPIC PATIENT – A SINGLE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This case study reports the successful management of vitreous floaters in a 23 year old myopic patient using *Ayurvedic* treatment protocols including *Panchakarma* therapies and herbal medications. The patient exhibited symptomatic relief with reduction in floater frequency and improved visual comfort following a 35 days *Ayurvedic* treatment. This study highlights *Ayurveda* potential role as a non-invasive therapeutic option for vitreous floaters associated with myopia.^{[1][2]}

KEYWORDS: vitreous floaters, myopia, *Ayurveda*, *Netra Tarpana*, *Panchakarma*, herbal therapy, case study.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

INTRODUCTION

Vitreous floaters known as *Drushti Dosha* or *Timira* in *Ayurveda*, are opacities in the vitreous humour that cast shadow on the retina cause visual disturbances often worsening in myopic individuals due to vitreous degeneration secondary to

elongation of eyeball. In *Ayurveda* such ocular disturbances occur due to imbalance in the *Vata Dosha* affecting the eyes. This case study explores an integrative *Ayurvedic* approach for managing floaters in a myopic patient.^{[1],[2],[3]}

AIM

1. To evaluate the clinical effectiveness and safety of *Ayurveda* treatment protocols in reducing vitreous floaters and associated visual discomfort in patient diagnosed with myopia.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the reduction in frequency and size of vitreous floaters in myopia patients following *Ayurveda* therapies.
2. To evaluate improvement in visual comfort and quality of life using subjective and objective measure.
3. To provide clinical evidence supporting *Ayurveda* as an adjunctive or alternative treatment approach for vitreous floaters in myopic eye.

CASE REPORT

A 23 year old female patient comes to *Shalakyatantra* OPD of Om *Ayurved* medical college and hospital, Betul with following complaints.

Age/sex – 23 years female

Medical History – mild myopia

No history of any surgeries or systemic illness

Chief complaints - diminished of vision

- Floaters in front of both eye (black spot)

Since 6 to 8 month

Refraction

	Right eye	Left eye
Spherical	-2.50	-2.50
Cylindrical	-0.50	-0.50
Axis	100	30
V/A	6/6	6/6

Clinical findings

Visual acuity - 6/6 in both eyes with correction

Anterior segment – normal on slit lamp examination

Fundus examination – in both eye Vitreous floaters observed along with myopic fundus. (indirect ophthalmoscopy) No retinal tear/detachment observed.

Intraocular pressure – normal

Diagnostic Assessments

Based on symptoms and examination, the condition was diagnosed as *Vataja Timira* with features of *Drushti Dosha* (Vitreous floaters). The primary *dosha* involved was *Vata*, with secondary involvement of *Pitta* due to dryness and strain. Diagnosis of symptomatic vitreous floaters in a myopic patient confirmed by clinical examination and history.^{[1],[3]}

Management protocol

Therapeutic intervention

Panchakarma

- *Netra tarpana* with *Mahatriphala Grhita* for 10 min was given daily for 7 days with 7 days gap (3 settings for 35 days).
- *Nasya – Anu tail* nasal drops – 2 drops per nostrils daily for 35 days.^{[3],[5]}

Herbal medication

- *Triphala churna* – 3g twice a daily with warm water for 35 days
- *Ashwagandha extract* – 500mg twice a daily for 35 days.^{[3],[4]}

Lifestyle and Dietary Advice

- avoidance of excessive screen time
- Balanced diet rich in antioxidants.
- Adequate hydration and regular eye exercise.^{[2],[4]}

OBSERVATION

Follow-up and outcomes

After completion of treatment, the efficacy of therapy was assessed on the basis of subjective as well as objective criteria. The patient was assessed twice before the treatment and after every 7 days of therapy and assessed subjective and objective criteria.

Subjective Criteria

Discomfort, diminished of vision and frequency of black spot in front of eye is decreases.

Objective Criteria

- After completion of treatment, the patient reported approximately 70% reduction in floater frequency and visual disturbance.
- Visualization of vitreous opacity – presence of discrete, mobile opacities seen within the vitreous cavity during indirect ophthalmoscopy is **decreases**.
- Visual analogue scale for discomfort decreased from 7/10 to 2/10
- Ophthalmic re-examination showed no adverse effects – slight clearing in vitreous cloudiness noted.
- Patient expresses improved quality of life and satisfaction.^{[1],[6]}

DISCUSSION

Ayurvedic management of vitreous floaters in myopic patients focuses on balancing of *Vata dosha*, strengthening ocular tissues, and improving circulation. *Tarpana* and *Nasya* are effective in nourishing the eyes and clearing vitreous opacities. Herbal supplements with antioxidant properties likely aid in reducing oxidative stress in the vitreous humour.

This case demonstrates the potential of *Ayurvedic* treatment modalities targeted at *Vata dosha* normalization in reducing symptoms of vitreous floaters in myopia. *Panchakarma* therapies such as *Netra Tarpana* may promote ocular nourishment and detoxification. Herbal supplements with antioxidant properties likely aid in reducing oxidative stress in the vitreous humour.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic management provided significant symptomatic relief for vitreous floaters in a myopic patient without complications. This integrative approach can be considered as a complementary option in similar case pending larger clinical validations.

Patient Consent

Informed consent was obtained from the patient for treatment and publication of this case study.

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